

***Myllocerus* Spp., Serious Pest Of Tree Seedlings In Forest Nurseries Of North-Western And Central India**

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The Coleopteran (Beetles and Weevils) is one of the most economic importance insect orders due to its feeding habits diversity and damage potential to number of forestry, agricultural and horticultural crops and biocontrol agents against the harmful insect pests (Stebbing, 1977). The weevils (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) are recognized as pests of forestry and agricultural crop which damage fruits, seeds, roots and leaves of seedlings/sampling, crops and also grains. More than 85,000 species of weevils belonging to 4144 genera have been reported from the different parts of the world (O'Brien & Wibmer 1978). They are mainly associated with seeds, seedlings/sampling, cereal, pulse, vegetable, fruit, forestry, plantation and horticulture crops. Some weevils are biocontrol agents other have medicinal importance and some have nutritional value (Marshall, 1916). Among these *Myllocerus* species are more economic importance.

The genus *Myllocerus* belong to the order Coleoptera, family-Curculionidae and subfamily Otiorrhynchinae. It is characterised by the presence of rostrum being with the head, antennae with scale extending beyond the front margin of thorax, fore coxae almost in the middle of posternum, femora dentate and claws always free. About 336 species of genus *Myllocerus* Schoenherr are known from the world recognized as valid in this genus, from Southeast Asia, the Indian subcontinent, Africa, Asia (including China and Japan), the Palearctic,

Indonesia and Australia (Ramamurthy and Ghai, 1988). *Myllocerus* species have already been reported as a notorious pest of several ornamental, horticultural and agro-forestry plants (Marshall, 1916; Beeson, 1941; Browne, 1968; Batra *et al.*, 1969; Butani & Jotwani, 1984; Swaminathan & Verma, 1991; Kumar & Ahmed, 1997). So far 89 species are reported from India, out of which 34 species are recorded as pest of forest trees causing defoliation of forest tree seedlings and forest trees (Beeson, 1941).

Seven species of *Myllocerus* viz; *Myllocerus dalbergiae*, *Myllocerus cardoni*, *M. dorsatus*, *M. laetivirens*, *M. tenuicornis* and *M. undecimputalatus*, and *M. discolor* are reported as serious pests of forest tree seedlings in nurseries of arid and semi-arid zone of Rajasthan, Western India and tropical forest areas of Maharashtra, Central India.

1. *Myllocerus dalbergiae* Rammamurthy

Adult measure 5.5 to 5.8 mm in length and 2.15 to 2.15 mm in breadth. Colour varies from light green to dark green. Head with eyes lateral. Rostrum twice as long as broad, about as long as head. Antennae black covered with dull white scales. Prothorax broader than long, apex as broad as base, side are smooth and surround.

Host plants: *Dalbergia sissoo*, *Moringa oleifera*

Distribution: New Delhi, Rajasthan: Jodhpur, Pali, Sikar, Nagur, Jhunjhunu.

Remarks: Reported as pests of *Moringa oleifera* and *Dalbergia sisoo*.

1. *Mylocerus cardoni* Marshall.

It is about 4mm long. Scales on intervals golden yellow with greenish tinge, circular on the strial margins.

Host plants : Pearl millet, napier grass, *Dalbergia sisoo*, *Butea frondosa*, *Acacia senegal*, *A.tortalis*, *Lagerstroemias* sp., *Schleichora oleosa*, *Hacourtia ramontchi*, *Poinciana regia*, *Populus* sp.,

Distribution: Bihar, Rajasthan (Udaipur, Jodhpur, Bikaner, Jaisalmer), Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal.

Remarks: Pest of *Dalbergia sisoo* and *Acacia tortalis*.

2. *Mylocerus dorsatus* Fabricius

Scales on intervals ovate with pedicel, radish pink with central parts green or circular without pedicel, metallic green. Scales on strial margin elongate, curved golden yellowish-green or ovate with straight apex and golden yellowish-green in colour.

Host plants: Potato, sword bean, lemon, cotton, mulberry, margodsa, *Tectona grandis*, *Satalum album*, *Toona senegal*, *Toona australis*, *Azadirachata indica*.

Distribution: Assam, Bihar, Karnataka, West Bengal, Maharashtra, New Delhi, Pondicherry, Tamil Nadu, Rajasthan and Gujarat.

Remarks: Pest of Neem.

3. *Mylocerus laetivirens* Marshall

Adults are small, 3 to 4 mm long, green with yellow tinge. Scales on the elytra are at intervals, the predominant circular without pedicel and the less predominant circular with narrow and small pedicel, both having metallic green colour with yellowish tinge. Scale on the spiral margins are cylindrical, yellowish green.

Host plants : Maize, cotton, pigeon, pea ,cow pea, soyabean, castor, okia, licere, sunhemp, phaselouse, ber plum, almond, apicort, mulberry, apple, mango, citrus, pomegranate, *Acacia senegal*, pear, strawberry, *Tectona grandis*, Neem.

Distribution: New Delhi, Rajasthan and elsewhere Pakistan.

Remarks: Cause extensive damage to horticulture crops, neem, *Moringa oleifera*, *Tecomella undulate*, *A. senegal*.

4. *Mylocerus tenuicornis* Faust

Adults 4 mm-5.5 long. Green black patches. Scales on intervals of two types, metallic green in colour with brown ridges, setae on the strial margins very long, elongate, hair like, erect, golden yellow with inner core brown.

Host plants: Plumes, Acalypha and Neem.

Distribution: Bihar, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Rajasthan and Tamil Nadu.

Remarks: Pest of Neem.

5. *Mylocerus undecimpustulatus* Faust

Greyish-white, spotted with black to greyish pink, 4-6 mm in length.

Host range: Gloriosa superb, Apricot plumes, peach, pea, rice, maize, pigeonpea, cotton, jute, sunflower, guava, mango, pomegranate, ber, litchi, strawberry, apple, *Dalbergia sisoo*, *Causrina equisetifolia*, *Acacia tortalis*, *Acacia senegal*.

Distribution: Bihar, Rajasthan (Jodhpur, Jaisalemer), Jharkhand (Ranchi).

Remarks: Pest of Neem.

6. *Mylocerus discolor* Boheman.

Dorsal surface is ferruginous brown, with patches of fawn-colored scaling and mottled black.

Host range: maize, sugarcane, sunflower, citrus, mango, jute, brinjal, soyabean, litchi, Mulberry (*Morus alba*) and *Dalbergia sisoo*

Distribution: Maharashtra (Nagpur, Kolhapur), Madhya Pradesh (Indore), Assam, Andhra Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir, Karnataka, Odisha

Remarks: Pest of Teak.

Habitat:

All *Mylocerus* species feed on the leaves. Some species are attracted to light. 2 to 4 adults are found congregating on the under surface of leaves, on the upright shoots and shoots tips. They are also seen on the stem near ground levels or as the ground in between plants. The eggs are laid in soil and larval stages also pass in soil. The larvae lived in soil and fed utterly on

the rootlet of grasses, host and annual plants. The adults start emerging in the beginning of April. The population reaches its maximum by August-September and starts decline by the end of October.

Nature of damage:

The adults are defoliators and cause damage by completely defoliating the plant. Initially a small hole is seen in the leaflet and gradually the entire leaf is eaten leaving the midrib. The larvae cut a hole at the 3-4 cm above from tip of the main root. It enters through it and feeds on the internal tissues making tunnel and keeps advancing upwards, making tunnel. The root becomes hollow, up to 30 – 40 mm from the point of entry. The attacked seedlings or plants eventually succumb to the injury and died.

Control:

Spray of monocrotophos 36 sl@ 1 ml/litre in the month of August-September when the population is at its peak controls the pest population build up.

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